

Safe & Sustainable by Design

Thought starter by RIVM (NL), March 19, 2021

This thought starter has been prepared for the European Commission stakeholders workshop 'Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) criteria for chemicals, materials and products' (March 19, 2021). We briefly discuss some insights from our work in Safe-by-Design (SbD) as well as safety and sustainability analysis more broadly. As such, this document does not reflect a formal position, but is meant to inform discussions about SSbD as a concept and the question by what kind of criteria SSbD practices can be advanced.

The [European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability \(CSS\)](#) features Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) as a prominent strategy for enabling the green and digital transitions in economy and society. SSbD ensures that research, design and innovation processes maximise safety and sustainability from the start through collaborations with experts, value chain actors and stakeholders as appropriate. SSbD criteria can support this at the level of individual organisations as well as innovation eco-systems, orienting both towards safe and sustainable futures.

SSbD practices

The CSS envisages SSbD as a transition from *managing* the harmful effects of chemical substances towards the *prevention* of these effects. Such a proactive approach requires design processes that:

- start from the question how a particular function can be best delivered;
- take a circular view as key to maximise safety and sustainability in production as well as multiple life cycles, designing out waste and hazardous substances;
- facilitate close collaboration between developers and relevant experts (e.g. toxicologists, life cycle analysts), value chain actors (e.g. producers, suppliers, users) and other stakeholders where appropriate;
- apply an iterative approach, moving forward in an inevitable context of uncertainty;
- are tailored to various design stages: chemical design in R&D stages, product design during innovation phase, etc.

→ Criteria for stimulating these characteristics will be needed next to outcome indicators (e.g. performance criteria).

Cultivating new innovation eco-systems

The CSS also calls for performance indicators measuring the transition to SSbD. Defining such criteria can be linked to various measures, ranging from knowledge and methodology development, (data-) infrastructure and platforms for interaction to education and economic and legal incentives. For example, in the Netherlands a range of Safe-by-Design (SbD) activities have been initiated. Main areas and examples are¹:

- **Research:** research for SbD has been covering multiple areas. Especially in the field of nanosafety, participation in (EU) research projects stimulated knowledge and methodology development as well as toolboxes and models for interaction between regulators and innovators. A [Safe Chemical Innovation Agenda](#) for alternatives development taking a functional approach contributed to the [SusChem research and innovation agenda](#).

¹ For more information and activities, see [SbD-NL website](#)

- **Education:** current and future scientists and engineers, business leaders and policy makers will require a novel set of competencies allowing for the integration of a much wider scope of needs and potential issues throughout the innovation process. Together with universities options for integrating SSbD skills in curricula are being explored.
- **Industry:** facilitating pilot projects (e.g. non-chemical alternatives for antifouling) and sector initiatives (e.g. circular design of mattresses) as well as feasibility research of chemical process intensification. Supporting government – business interactions are the [Safe Innovation Approach](#) and [Safe and Sustainable Material Loops](#) framework for material recycling.

→ Accelerating the transition to SSbD depends on how well various measures, including regulatory drivers, enforce each other. Transition criteria will have to support those synergies.

Future orientations

Taking circularity seriously

The transition to a circular economy shifts the attention to material loops and post-use. Office paper, for example, can be recycled up to approximately seven times as office paper. When fibers become too short, next stages may include downcycling in cardboard or toilet paper, until final return into the biosphere (via waste water, compost or ash). The design and composition of office paper therefore has to take into account the subsequent stages, for which all components, such as inks, as well as processes, have to be designed safe and sustainable. In the technosphere, similar comprehensive approaches will be required. For example, in analyzing [railway sleeper alternatives](#), issues to be accounted for range from estimated life span to regulatory provisions in waste handling. Safe and sustainability performance therefore is crucially dependent on exploring circular strategies together with experts and stakeholders, cherishing the user orientation of design thinking.

Anticipating new uncertainties

New materials may hold the key for innovative solutions enabling the green and digital transitions of our economy and society, but also come with new uncertainties. Anticipating these, comes with two main challenges. First, foresight and assessment approaches have to match various design stages, from chemical design to product design, ranging from early screening to full assessments. Moreover, as we have seen for nanomaterials, safe innovation requires better interaction between innovators and regulators, so as to proactively address uncertainties inherently linked to exploring and exploiting novel material properties.

Innovating innovation

Knowledge, strategies and methodologies for SSbD as well as production technologies will be continuously developing. For example, new data and machine learning tools may provide options to assess the intrinsic hazardous properties of new substances and materials upfront. Still, trade-offs as well as uncertainties will remain and new issues, such as unintended effects, may emerge. Corporate sustainable governance strategies and circular business models therefore have to support capacities for learning, prioritization and selection of options for continuous improvement. Furthermore, digital infrastructures are being developed to enable information flows related to material loops.

→ When evaluating SSbD criteria and transition indicators, new developments in knowledge, methodologies and technologies can be accounted for. The other way around, SSbD criteria and indicators can help navigating these developments.

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